

Von Neumann Entropy and Nonorthogonal States

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. And San Pier Niceto, Messina Nov. 8, 2023

The von Neumann entropy: $-\text{Trace}(\rho \ln(\rho))$, which is applied to a set of quantum mechanical states, is similar in form to Shannon's entropy, $-\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$. In fact, the two are equal if the density matrix is diagonal with $P(i)$ as the eigenvalues and $\sum_i P(i)=1$. In the literature (1), it is noted that the value of the von Neumann entropy may change if one uses different basis states. This is considered a problem. If the states are created using a unitary operator acting on an original orthonormal set, then (2) shows that the von Neumann entropy is unchanged. In general (1), however, this is not the case. (1) suggests that one should find the set of states which yield the lowest Shannon entropy.

We try to argue that the origins of the form: $P(i) \ln(P(i))$ in classical statistical mechanics follow from the independence of probabilities and the nonoverlap of their states and try to extend this idea to quantum states. For a set of states which yield a diagonal density matrix, unitary transformations yield a set of basis states which are still orthonormal, i.e. independent. If one uses states which are not orthogonal as a basis, the states are no longer independent even though one still has a set of $P(i)$ which sum to 1. We consider a 2 state orthogonal system (eigenfunctions of a Hamiltonian) and simultaneously of an operator A (i.e. $[H,A]=0$). We define density operators as: $\rho = \sum_i p(i) |i\rangle\langle i|$ whether or not the states i are orthogonal and insist that $\langle A \rangle$ be the same regardless of the basis used. In the two-state case, this may lead to different von Neumann entropy values for states which are not created by a unitary transform of the initial two energy eigenstates. We argue that the $p(1)=p(2) = .5$ eigenstate represents an extremization of entropy and that a shift to nonorthogonal states leads to a higher negative entropy. We also argue that nonorthogonal states have an overlap and so are not independent whereas physically the probabilities used classically are associated with states which do not overlap, i.e. a heads up or down coin represent nonoverlapping states.

Von Neumann Entropy

The von Neumann entropy was introduced to link quantum mechanics with classical thermodynamics/statistical mechanics. The form used is reminiscent of the Shannon's entropy form:

$$-\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i)) \quad ((1))$$

i.e.

a density operator ρ is introduced, $\rho = \sum_i P(i) |i\rangle\langle i|$ such that i is a state (not necessarily orthogonal) and $\sum_i P(i)=1$.

$$\text{Then: } S_{\text{von Neumann}} = -\text{Trace}(\rho \ln(\rho)) \quad ((2))$$

In the case that ρ is diagonal, with $P(i)$ as eigenvalues, one may use a power series expansion for \ln and one sees that the eigenvalues are independent, i.e. do not mix. The Trace becomes a sum of the diagonal elements which are $-P(i) \ln(P(i))$. This is exactly the Shannon's entropy result, and so for such a case the quantum and classical results coincide.

If one takes a unitary transformation of the basis which diagonalizes ρ , then the von Neumann entropy remains unchanged as stated in (2).

Consider $\rho \rightarrow \rho' = U(\text{transpose}) \rho U$, where U is a unitary matrix. Then:

$-\text{Trace}(d' \ln(d')) = -\text{Trace}(U(\text{trans}) d \ln(d) U)$ where d is diagonal

$= -\sum_{ij} U(\text{trans})_{ij} D_{jl} U_{li}$ where $D_{jl} = (d \ln(d))_{jl}$

Holding j, l constant, $\sum_i U_{li} U(\text{trans})_{ij} = \delta_{ij}$ so

$-\text{Trace}(d' \ln(d')) = \text{Trace}(d \ln(d))$ where d is diagonal ((3))

If one restricts oneself to an orthonormal basis set which diagonalizes d or unitary transformations of such a basis one has Shannon's entropy. There is, however, no mathematical restriction from having a basis set which is not orthonormal. In such a case, we argue that the value of von Neumann's entropy may change. This has been noted in the literature many times (1). In other words, the von Neumann entropy depends on the basis chosen, while no such situation occurs in classical statistical mechanics. In (1) it is suggested that one use the basis set which minimizes Shannon's entropy. Other basis sets would be considered incorrect. Thus, a kind of selection rule is imposed. We suggest that this rule may be associated with behaviour of probability and its associated states in classical statistical mechanics. There, the states are nonoverlapping (e.g. a coin). We suggest then that classical statistical mechanics is based on probabilities associated with nonoverlapping states.

Classical Statistical Mechanics and Shannon's Entropy

It seems that classical mechanics is based on using probabilities associated with nonoverlapping states. For example, there is no overlap between a heads-up and heads-down state of a coin, or a state of a die. The statement of independent probabilities seems to be extended to including nonoverlapping states, we argue. In such a case, the idea of entropy is to average information $\ln(P(i))$ for each independent, nonoverlapping state. As a result, there seems to be a direct link to orthonormal states in quantum mechanics (e.g. eigenstates of the Hamiltonian).

Consider Shannon's entropy in two different ways. The first is to consider nonoverlapping states and independent probability and to compute an overall probability of N trial runs. In such a case, for N being very large, one has:

Probability for a trial of N runs: $\prod_i p(i)^{N p(i)}$ ((4))

For large N , then, each trial has the same probability. Taking \ln of this value yields a sum showing the independence of the probabilities:

$\ln(\text{Probability}) = \sum_i p(i) N \ln(p(i))$ ((5))

Alternatively, consider a total energy E distributed over N particles. At first, there is not total independence due to a constraint on the total energy, so $n(e_i)$ = number of particles with energy e_i cannot be completely independent. If one lifts this and only constrains average energy, one has nonoverlapping states and independence. The number of ways to distribute energy over N particles is:

$N! / \prod_i n(e_i)!$ ((6))

Using Stirling's approximation for large $n(e_i)$ (hence N) and taking \ln of ((6)) yields: $\ln(N!) - \sum_i n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i))$ ((7))

As a result, we suggest that linking quantum mechanics to statistical mechanics should incorporate two ideas:

(A) independent probabilities

(B) nonoverlapping states

How does one ensure that states in quantum mechanics are nonoverlapping? One may use orthonormal states which follow as eigenfunctions of Hermitian operators, such as the Hamiltonian.

Orthogonal States

We consider a two eigenfunction set of a Hamiltonian system, where the Hamiltonian commutes with an operator A. The two states are $I+\rangle$ and $I-\rangle$. What probability weights should they have? Like in classical statistical mechanics, we consider maximizing Shannon's entropy subject to the constraint: $p_1+p_2=1$, because the von Neumann entropy for a diagonal density matches Shannon's entropy. This leads to $p_1=p_2=.5$ as the extremized value. Other shifts in p_1 and p_2 away from this lead to lower entropy. We argue that changing from the $I+\rangle, I-\rangle$ basis to a nonorthonormal one shifts p_1 and p_2 away from .5 and hence leads to a nonextreme entropy. We thus rule out such entropy, i.e. such orthonormal states. This leads to a selection rule based on the use of the orthonormal eigenstates of H and its commuting A operator. We consider some specific examples.

Consider the basis set (eigenfunctions of H) $I+\rangle$ and $I-\rangle$ and probability weights .5 and .5.

Next, consider the orthonormal set, obtained by a unitary transformation:

$1/\sqrt{2} [I+\rangle + I-\rangle]$ and $1/\sqrt{2} [I+\rangle - I-\rangle]$ with weight p_1 and p_2 such that $p_1+p_2=1$

We use an operator A which commutes with H and insist that $\langle A \rangle$ be the same for both basis sets. $\langle A \rangle = \text{Trace} (\rho A)$ in the von Neumann scheme. Let A acting on a + state yield an eigenvalue of 1 and on -, 2. Then:

$$.5 + .5(2) = p_1 .5 (1+2) + p_2 .5 (1+2) \text{ or } p_1 + p_2 = 1 \quad ((7))$$

Thus, no new constraint is imposed. The values of p_1 and p_2 which maximize entropy are .5, .5 so the unitary transformation does not change Shannon's entropy, i.e. von Neumann entropy in this case. What about a non-orthonormal transformation using states:

$I+\rangle$ and $1/\sqrt{2} [I+\rangle + I-\rangle]$ Enforcing the constancy of $\langle A \rangle$ yields:

$$.5 + .5(2) = p_1 + p_2 .5 (1+2) \text{ where } p_1+p_2=1 \text{ so } p_2=1, p_1=0$$

This leads to a different Shannon's entropy of 0. Given that $p_1=p_2=.5$ maximized negative entropy at some negative value, one knows that a shift in p_2, p_1 yields a higher entropy. A shift in p_1, p_2 , however, is guaranteed by the use of nonorthonormal states as seen directly above. This automatically increases the entropy and so we rule it out.

In (1), a similar approach is used in that the authors suggest that in the quantum mechanical case one use a basis set which minimizes Shannon's entropy. The point seems to be that one must force a selection rule on basis states. We suggest using states which are orthonormal and these seem to follow automatically eigenfunctions of a Hamiltonian, for example.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it has been often noted in the literature (1) that von Neumann's entropy may depend

on the basis set used. In the case of a diagonal density matrix, von Neumann's entropy is equivalent to Shannon's entropy using the diagonal entries as probabilities.

We consider two eigenstates of a Hamiltonian which commutes with an operator A. The density operator, with probability weights p_1 and p_2 , for these states which maximizes entropy subject to the constraint $p_1+p_2=1$ is $.5 |I+\rangle + .5 |I-\rangle$. A unitary transformation of the states $|I+\rangle, |I-\rangle$ leaves the von Neumann entropy unchanged, as stated in (2), but a change to a nonorthonormal basis set does not. It automatically moves p_1, p_2 away from $.5$, i.e. to a higher negative entropy value. Thus, we reject such bases, even though they exist mathematically, because they move away from extreme entropy.

In the example we use, we enforce the criteria that an operator A commutes with Hamiltonian H and that $\langle A \rangle$ is the same whichever basis is used.

References

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